

Title: Seriation as a tool to unravel the chronology of ceramist pre-colonial groups from São Paulo State, Brazil: boundaries, contacts, and identities

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Abstract

Chronologies are fundamental elements for a deeper understanding of the dynamics of human exploration of landscapes in past times. This project focused on Tupiguarani ceramist groups from the Late Holocene in the state of São Paulo, specifically in the Paranapanema, Ribeira do Iguape, and Tietê Valleys. Pottery collections from 15 sites in these three regions were gathered, prioritizing technological, morphological, and decorative aspects. By employing statistical methods, including the use of cladistics, and Cultural Transmission Theory, we aimed to comprehend the historical boundaries and contacts of these human groups. Additionally, we sought to contribute to the discussion on how artifactual variability and relative chronology can be utilized to gain a better understanding of the past occupation of these landscapes. This report will describe the activities undertaken during the internship at the University of Auckland between August 1st and November 3rd, as well as the by-products, which are articles that will be submitted for publication. Drawing from the literature consulted, this report provides an opportunity to introduce some of the theoretical and methodological aspects that we had the opportunity to learn during the internship.

Key word: Evolutionary Archaeology, Cultural Transmission Theory, Tupiguarani Tradition, Multivariate Statistics, São Paulo's Archaeology,

Introduction

This report aims to present the activities undertaken during the internship and the theoretical and methodological issues learned. The internship took place between August 1st and November 3rd, 2023. The return to Brazil in early November was documented in the Change Request submitted to FAPESP (Process: 2023/03591-1). One notable event was the planned participation in the International Event in Morocco (RENA 2023 - 2ème Édition Congrès – Ressources Naturelles & Développement Durable - Faculté des Sciences et Techniques de Fès and Université Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdella de Fès, Fès, Morocco), which did not occur as intended (due to the denial of assistance by FAPESP - Process 2023/12186-3 presented by Gregório Ceccantinni, PhD). Despite the denial, remote participation in the congress took place to disseminate the first results obtained during this internship.

Although the primary motivation for this internship was to understand how changes in material culture occur, achieving this result involved learning how to apply statistical methods, particularly the principles of phylogenesis, including cladistics, which is a significant tool grouping taxa based on hypotheses of evolutionary relationships. All these terms will be explained in this report.

Cultural change is a wide discussion among archaeologists and can be explained by three possible factors: 1) parallel and convergent adaptation to similar selective pressures; 2) common ancestry with the inheritance of culture by future generations and processes of cultural ramification; 3) horizontal transmission through intergroup interaction (blending) (O'BRIEN, BUCHANA, COLLARD, BOULANGER, 2012; CREMA, KERIG, SHENAN 2014). O'Brien et al. (2012) argue that there is growth in this type of approach, as the scientific community has recognized that the transmission of cultural traits can be studied in a way similar to genetic transmission, observing the systems that involve these processes.

Ignoring examples of adaptive convergent evolution (cultural traits arising in different places due to group adaptation to the environment) and focusing exclusively on neutral traits (traits arising through innovation or interethnic contact) (DUNNELL, 1971), the cultural similarities or differences observed between two communities can be explained through the results of branches and mixtures that may have occurred over time (CREMA, KERIG, SHENAN 2014).

The Tupiguarani Tradition was developed along the lines of the National Archaeological Research Program (PRONAPA), which aimed to organize and group archaeological sites based on their similarities and differences within a specific definition of 'Cultural Tradition' (JANDIRA NETO, 2014). These definition templates were adaptations presented by Willey and Philips (1958), concerned with providing references for organizing sites based on parameters of temporality, shapes, and spatiality.

In general, archaeologists understand the Tupiguarani Tradition as the result of the organization and grouping of sites that present similar characteristics within a certain temporality throughout the spatiality of South America. Correa (2014) explains the historiography and construction of the term associated with the Tupiguarani Tradition, compiling Ethnographic, Linguistic, Ethno-Historical, and Archaeological datasets. From these parameters, we have the Tupiguarani archaeological jargon defined by Meggers (1967) with definitions made from typologies perceived from the archaeological record. Thus, in that period, it was established that this term would be associated with ceramic sites that presented polychromatic painting (red or black on white or red engobe), outside the region delimited by the Amazon Basin, with plastic finishing techniques predominating on smoothed, corrugated surfaces, unglazed or brushed, and engobe. In addition to these characteristics, the presence of secondary burials would be recognized, with the presence of urns, polished stone axes, tembetás, chips, cutters, and scorches (BROCHADO, et al., 1969; TERMINOLOGIA, 1976; BROCHADO, 1981, CORREA, 2014).

For this analysis, 15 archaeological sites associated with the Tupiguarani Tradition spread across the State of São Paulo territory were incorporated, where we had access to the archaeological collections stored at the Museum of Archaeology and Ethnology (MAE/USP/Brazil) and at the Regional Center for Environmental Archaeology (Centro Regional de Arqueologia Ambiental Mário Neme - CRAMN/MAE-USP/Piraju/São Paulo/Brazil). This report aims to demonstrate how the debate involving cladistics, a rich set of tools borrowed from Biological Sciences, is robust enough to draw archaeological inferences about the evolutionary history of a human population. All these issues were learned during the internship at the University of Auckland, Auckland, New Zealand.

Methods

The method learned during the internship was applied to the Tupiguarani Tradition dataset. The method aims to verify the presence or absence of homologies and homoplasies involving the dispersion of populations associated with Tupiguarani pottery in the state of São Paulo. We applied the protocol described by O'Brien and Lyman (2003), Garcia-Rivero and O'Brien (2014), and Cochrane (2015). This protocol aims to convert the attributes into presence and absence, resulting in a cladistic tree.

Initially, we analyzed the collections of archaeological sites spread across the São Paulo territory that presented numerically representative collections associated with the Tupiguarani Tradition, including sites with known ages. Table 1 presents the sites involved in this analysis, based on Perez (2018, 2022, 2023). The sites Prema Tupi, Sao Cardoso/Sao Geraldo, De Rosa, and Dourado 2 do not have recorded ages, but they were included in the research so that a possible chronological approximation could be established for them following the protocol.

Table 1 - Sites used for cladistic analysis and elaborations.

Sites	Municipalities	Total Sherds analyzed	Collection location	Ages	References
Itaguá	Ubatuba	1485	MAE/USP/SP	660±80	UCHOA, SCATAMACCHIA, GARCIA, 1984.
Mineração	Iguape	1287	MAE/USP/SP	560 BP	SCATAMACCHIA, UCHÔA, 1993
Prema Tupi	Rio Claro	1136	-	-	PEREZ, 2012
Gramado	Brotas	700	MAE/USP/SP	190±20	MORAES, 2007
Nunes	Piraju	383	CRAMN/MAE-USP	880±90, 879±90	MORAIS, 1985
Alves	Piraju	375	CRAMN/MAE-USP	1150±100, 1020 BP, 955±100, 1021±100	NOELLI, 1999-2000
Lambari II	Casa Branca	372	MAE/USP/SP	1085±130	MORAES, 2007
Fonseca	Itapeva	371	MAE/USP/SP e CRAMN/MAE-USP	1100±110, 1010±100, 1076 AP, 1190±120, 970±100, 1100±110, 899 AD	ARAUJO, 2001
Sao Cardoso/Sao Geraldo	Arealva	369	MAE/USP/SP	-	MORAES, 2007
Almeida	Tejupá	347	CRAMN/MAE-USP	1400 AD, 560±60, 470±50	SCATAMACCHIA, 1981
De Rosa	Ibitinga	310	MAE/USP/SP	-	MORAES, 2007
Bianco	Itapeva	283	MAE/USP/SP	295±30	ARAUJO, 2001
Mata da Figueira	Cândido Mota	246	CRAMN/MAE-USP	340±35	MORAIS, 2001

Sites	Municipalities	Total Sherds analyzed	Collection location	Ages	References
Dourado 2	Promissão	165	MAE/USP/SP	-	ARAUJO et al., 2022
Pajeú	Cândido Mota	136	CRAMN/MAE-USP	875±90, 340±35, 607 BP	MORAES, 2007

The next step involved applying a Heuristic analysis with a repetition of 10,000 times. This poll is utilized by the software itself, aiming to discover the best configuration options for the branches of each arm of a tree. In other words, the program searched for the optimal option 10,000 times for each elaborated branch of each tree. To generate each tree, the Almeida site was selected as an outgroup due to its older age. Other attempts to incorporate the Fonseca site or the Alves site as members of the outgroup did not yield satisfactory results, as the software used did not permit the inclusion of two or more representatives as outgroups.

The conversion of attributes identified for each site resulted in matrices with a total of 567 characters for each site included in this analysis. Table 2 presents the diagram followed for data intersection.

Table 2 - Diagram of the preparation of matrices used in the analysis.

Number of characters involved/ Types of characters	Painting	Temper	Rim shapes	Surface treatments and finishes
396	X			
42		X		
70			X	
59				X
438	X	X		
466	X		X	
455	X			X
112		X	X	
101		X		X
129			X	X
497	X	X	X	
567	X	X	X	X

The conversion of data into matrices was performed in Excel, saved in '.txt' format with tabulated separation. In the Notepad application, tabs were removed, and all matrices were organized for analysis using PAUP* software version 4.0, with the #NEXUS extension as specified by the software developer.

Activities developed at the University of Auckland

During the internship period, I had the opportunity to attend the course “Pacific Archaeology – ANTH 306”, taught by Ethan E. Cochrane, PhD. This course aimed to cover key aspects of Oceania's Archaeology, including discussions on human settlements in Micronesia, Late Society Islands, Oceanic languages, Origins of the Polynesians, Paleoenvironmental records and Archaeology, Humans and Pacific environments, Explaining changes in the complexity of Chiefdoms, Socio-Political Variation, with evolution and behavioral ecology, Rapa Nui and the "collapse" of society, Colonial history and Archaeology, and European and Pacific Population.

Additionally, I had the opportunity to participate in the course “An Introduction to Geometric Morphometrics” taught by Mercedes Okumura, PhD. As the name suggests, it served as an introduction to understanding how to describe a shape, the fundamentals of Geometric Morphometrics (GMM), the history of GMM, the methodology, the use of landmarks, how to operate the software MorphoJ and TPSUtil, and the application of PCA (Principal Component Analysis) and cluster construction.

Throughout this internship period, I also attended various lectures.

Lecture “Population rise was the origin of Polynesian chiefdoms” – Ethan E. Cochrane, PhD. Anthropology Seminar – Owen Glenn Building, University of Auckland, Auckland, New Zealand.

Lecture “Birthing in the afterlife of slaving in Brazil” – Laura Caballe Climent, PhD. Anthropology Seminar – Owen Glenn Building, University of Auckland, Auckland, New Zealand.

Lecture “Who were the shellmound builders from Ribeira de Iguape Valley? A 10,000-years tale from southeastern Brazil. – Mercedes Okumura, PhD. Anthropology Seminar – Owen Glenn Building, University of Auckland, Auckland, New Zealand.

Lecture “Fuctualing Liminality in a cultural immersion trip” - Paul Malcolm Robertson, PhD. Anthropology Seminar – Owen Glenn Building, University of Auckland, Auckland, New Zealand.

Lecture “Case 32: a clash of cultures in the western Solomon Islands – a deep time perspective” - Peter Sheppard, PhD. Anthropology Seminar – Owen Glenn Building, University of Auckland, Auckland, New Zealand.

Furthermore, all the project activities were operationalized, including a list of readings, and I learned how to use PAUP* (Phylogenetic Analysis Using Parsimony). This software is designed for phylogenetic analysis using parsimony, maximum likelihood, and distance methods. Among the many strengths of the program are the rich array of options for dealing with phylogenetic trees, including importing, combining, comparing, constraining, rooting, and testing hypotheses.

Publications prepared or under preparation related to BEPE

During the internship period, I had the opportunity to draft three articles. While none of them are finalized, they are in an advanced stage of development. The titles of these articles are provided in the attached report. Additionally, a book chapter has been accepted for publication during this period. The outcomes of the research were presented at the International Seminar in Morocco.

Articles in preparation

PEREZ, Glauco Constantino; ARAUJO, Astolfo Gomes de Mello; OKUMURA, Mercedes; COCHRANE, Ethan E. *Uses of cladistic to understand the prehistory of the Sao Paulo State, Brazil*

PEREZ, Glauco Constantino; ARAUJO, Astolfo Gomes de Mello; OKUMURA, Mercedes; COCHRANE, Ethan E. *A Transmissão Cultural de grupos associados à Tradição Tupiguarani explicada através da Filogenia e Cladística.*

PEREZ, Glauco Constantino; ARAUJO, Astolfo Gomes de Mello; OKUMURA, Mercedes. *Curva do Coletor como teste de amostragem de sítios arqueológicos.*

Book chapter accepted for publication

PEREZ, Glauco Constantino. Um breve panorama sobre a cerâmica arqueológica no Estado de São Paulo – Brasil. IN: PERAZO, Marília; ARAUJO, Astolfo Gomes de Mello. *E-book do I Ciclo de Palestra Arqueologia e Patrimônio do MAE/USP*. Book chapter accepted for publication. 2023.

Participation in International scientific event and Oral presentation

PEREZ, Glauco Constantino; ARAUJO, Astolfo Gomes de Mello; OKUMURA, Mercedes; COCHRANE, Ethan E. The use of cladistics to explore cultural transmission among Tupiguarani groups in São Paulo State, Brazil. 2^{ème} Édition Congrès –

Ressources Naturelles & Développement Durable – RENA 2023. Faculté des Sciences et Techniques de Fès and Université Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdella de Fes. Morocco, 9-10 November 2023.

Data Management Plan

During the activities of this research, we also prepared the Data Management Plan, which was created using the DMPTool platform. In this plan, the raw data generated throughout the research will be made accessible. Consequently, all information will be available whenever other researchers interested in the topic of archaeological ceramics associated with the Tupiguarani Tradition in the State of São Paulo emerge. The data will be accessible for new cycles of analysis from fresh theoretical and methodological perspectives, eliminating the need for the re-analysis of the archaeological collections.

To access the full plan, go to: <https://doi.org/10.48321/D1D95P>

Results

The results of the internship can be explored in this section. The analyzed data will also be presented in a similar manner as demonstrated here in the articles that are currently under preparation.

Table 3 displays the results for the Consistency Index (CI) and Retention Index (RI). The ideal Retention Index (RI) for identifying a suitable dataset homology is always the value closest to one (1). In this table, it can be observed that the RI indicating the best configuration of the different trees created could be those using Temper characters (RI = 0.75) and All characters (RI = 0.62). The other configurations have RIs ranging between 0.37 and 0.53, which, as suggested, still present potential indications for analyses involving cultural data (COCHRANE & LIPO, 2010; COLLARD et al. 2008). The numbers presented in each branch represent the count of characters that differentiate each bifurcation between the analyzed taxa.

Table 3 - Indices generated from data analysis.

	Number of characters used	Tree length	Consistency index (CI)	Retention index (RI)
All characters	567	386	0.5207	0.6208
Painting	396	111	0.7297	0.4444
Temper	42	22	0.7273	0.7500
Rim Shape	70	143	0.4476	0.5325
Surface treatment and finishes	59	71	0.5634	0.4655
Painting and temper	438	142	0.6831	0.4231
Painting and rim shape	466	265	0.5472	0.4619
Painting and surface treatment and finishes	455	187	0.6471	0.4107
Temper and rim shape	112	177	0.4520	0.4974
Temper and surface treatment and finishes	101	104	0.3585	0.4146
Rim shape and surface treatment and finishes	129	228	0.4561	0.4537
Painting, surface treatment and finishes and temper	497	222	0.6171	0.3750

Table 4 show the results of the trees that was get with the PAUP* software use.

Table 4 - Cladistic trees created using Paup* software.

4) Rim Shape

5) Surface treatment and finishes

6) Paintin and temper

7) Painting and rim shape

8) Painting and surface treatment and finishes

9) Temper and rim shape

10) Temper and surface treatment and finishes

11) Rim shape and surface treatment and finishes

12) Painting, surface treatment and finishes and temper

Regarding Table 4, the trees are described to illustrate their particularities.

Tree 1: Presents the analysis of all characters, with the Almeida site as the outgroup. The Itaguá site appears as an outgroup of the composition, and the Mineração and Alves sites are close together, followed by the Fonseca site.

Tree 2: Analysis based on the use of painting, with the Almeida site as the outgroup. The Alves site appears as an outgroup of the composition generated by the combination of Mineração and Itaguá sites, reversed to the other inland sites.

Tree 3: Analysis made with temper characters, with the Almeida site as the outgroup. There is a combination with coastal sites in the last branch formed by the sites Mineração, Itaguá, Bianco, and De Rosa, representing sites from all analyzed regions.

Tree 4: Analysis based on rim shape, with the Almeida site as an outgroup. The composition of Mineração, Alves, and Fonseca sites appears, while the Itaguá site is an outgroup of the entire analyzed set.

Tree 5: Analysis based on surface treatment and finishing data, with the Almeida site as the chosen outgroup. Mineração and Itaguá sites appear together in a separate branch, while the Tietê and Paranapanema valley sites (inland sites) are mixed in other branches.

Tree 6: Union of painting and temper characters, with the Almeida site chosen as an outgroup. The composition of Mineração and Itaguá appears as a pair, and the inland sites are mixed.

Tree 7: Union of painting and rim shape, with the Almeida site as the outgroup. The composition between Mineração and Alves, followed by the Fonseca site, resembles the arrangement of the tree formed only by rim shape data (Tree 4).

Tree 8: Union of painting and surface treatment and finishes data, with the Almeida site as the outgroup. There is a composition of Mineração and Itaguá sites, while the inland sites are organized in other branches.

Tree 9: Union of temper and rim shape data, with the Almeida site as the outgroup. The composition of Mineração and Alves sites, followed by Fonseca, appears again, and the Itaguá site is in a branch together with the Sao Geraldo/Sao Cardoso site. This tree is similar to Trees 4 and 7.

Tree 10: Union of temper, surface treatment, and finishes characters, with the Almeida site as the outgroup. In this composition, the Mineração and Itaguá sites appear as a separate branch compared to the inland sites. This tree is similar to Tree 5.

Tree 11: Union of rim shape, surface treatment, and finishes characters, with the Almeida site as the outgroup. The composition of Mineração and Alves sites appears, followed by the Fonseca site.

Tree 12: Union of painting, surface treatment, finishes, and temper characters, with the Almeida site as the outgroup. The Mineração and Itaguá sites make up a separate branch from the inland sites. This tree is similar to Tree 8, in which painting and surface treatment and finishes data are combined.

In general, the combination of the Mineração site and Itaguá appears in seven trees (trees 2, 3, 5, 6, 8, 10, 12). When including the analysis based on painting and surface treatment and finishes, an organization with coastal sites is opposed to inland sites, even though sites in the Tietê and Paranapanema basins share branches on the trees. On the other hand, the combination of the Mineração and Alves sites followed by the Fonseca site appears five times (trees 1, 4, 7, 9, 11) when the rim shapes are analyzed, and there is no coastal and inland separation; all sites are mixed.

Regarding the exploratory analysis on the insertion of sites without known ages, the Dourado 2 and Prema Tupi sites form a branch in trees 1, 3, 4, 7, 9, and 11. These configurations are consistently associated with the Lambari II and Pajeu sites. Furthermore, Dourado 2 and Prema Tupi sites share the branch with the Gramado site in trees 2, 5, 6, and 10, suggesting some kind of proximity between them and possibly being closer in temporality.

The composition that shows a separation between the coast and the inland is observed in most of the analyses. This organization arises even with the inclusion of only two sites to represent the coast compared to 13 inland sites. A perspective of sampling bias is refuted because, even with the low number of coastal sites, the coastal-inland composition is the most common in the analysis carried out. Attributes of different types were also used for this analysis, including morphological, technological, and decorative aspects, totaling more than five hundred characters. In this way, sampling bias is completely discarded for this analysis.

Activity plan for the next period

In this section, we present the activities and future developments for the research. Building on the established connections with the institution and the research team abroad, we will have the opportunity for collaboration in the upcoming phase of the research, contributing to the interpretation of the results achieved in this stage of the work. The grantee, along with their supervisors both in the home country and abroad, commit to publishing a paper resulting from the internship activity. This publication will elucidate the methods and outcomes obtained, as previously mentioned in the preceding section, along with information on articles currently in preparation.

All activities and stages of the initial project research, as well as those proposed in this request, will be resumed in the first semester of 2024, with new theoretical and methodological collaborations facilitated by BEPE.

Table 5 systematizes all activities and planned deadlines for the years 2023 and 2024. In orange, the activities related to the Foreign Research Internship Grant (BEPE) are highlighted, and in gray, the activities to be carried out in the next period of the research grant.

Tabela 5 – Cronograma de atividades atuais.

Activity/ Semester	2nd semester of 2023	1st semester 2024	2nd semester 2024
BEPE Final Report Writing and Accountability			
Applying Wealth Tests to dataset			
Applying similarity tests to the dataset			
Applying Occurrence Seriation tests to the dataset			
Applying Frequency Seriation Tests to the dataset			
Applying Cladistic Tests to the dataset			
Compilation of the results with the statistical tests			
Class that will be offered at MAE/USP			
Adequacy of the Data Management Plan			
Training Extension Course			
Article Writing			
Preparation of the Final Report			

Contributions of the internship to research in Brazil

The report aims to present the activities carried out during the internship period at the University of Auckland, Auckland, New Zealand, between August and November 2023. The internship was supervised by Professor Dr. Ethan Cochrane in the Department of Anthropology at this university.

The research aimed to contribute, through the application of methods from Evolutionary Biology to the methodological discussion regarding the use of cladistics in cultural contexts. This was expressed in archaeological sites scattered throughout the state of São Paulo, with a particular focus on the basins of the Tietê, Ribeira do Iguape, and Paranapanema Rivers. Sites along the north and south coasts of the state were also involved.

The contribution of the overseas internship was to provide the grantee with adequate time to learn, become familiar with, apply, and develop methods that include cladistics as a research possibility for archaeological contexts. Additionally, there was the production of texts that will be submitted for international and national publication, as well as book chapters. All texts are original and directly result from the research conducted during the internship period.

The results of the internship support new methodological applications using cultural and technological inference data, contributing to understanding how prehistoric ceramic-producing groups might have dispersed in the territory. It also offers possible explanations about how their intergroup contacts might have occurred.

In this perspective, this work and the use of this specific method bring a unique contribution to Brazilian Archaeology by allowing a scientific approach with international literature that was previously inaccessible to Brazilian archaeologists. Furthermore, the method presented enables interpretative inferences from the archaeological data itself, allowing the research to be easily replicated by other researchers.

The report enriches the understanding of cultural and technological interactions throughout the territory of the state of São Paulo, contributing to knowledge construction in the field of São Paulo archaeology. The conclusions presented help consolidate the understanding of the cultural practices of these prehistoric communities and offer valuable insights into movements and potential areas of interaction.

Discussion And Conclusions

In this report, I had the opportunity to elucidate all the experiences gained during the internship at the University of Auckland. The project was supervised by Dr. Ethan E. Cochrane, who is the principal investigator of this research. I also received valuable contributions from Dr. Mercedes Okumura, who assisted in interpreting the results.

In this context, we applied cladistic methods to gain insights into one of the most significant archaeological questions, namely, potential interpretations of cultural change. Our case study focuses on pottery associated with the Tupiguarani Tradition in the state of São Paulo. Cladistics provides an objective approach to understanding hypotheses about the dispersal of this population, offering measures of similarity resulting from evolutionary relationships.

O'Brien et al. (2012) explained that this type of study was pioneered by paleontologist George Gaylord Simpson in the 1960s, providing an example to comprehend hypotheses of similarity and evolutionary relationships. They describe that monozygotic twins are not similar because they are twins, but rather they are twins because they are similar. In other words, they share a common history (O'BRIEN, BUCHANA, COLLARD, BOULANGER, 2012). In this context, cladistics assists in understanding this common history, whether it pertains to organisms or objects of material culture, such as projectile points or pottery vessels, as addressed in this article.

Considerations must be given to factors such as the longevity of these populations in the territory of the State of São Paulo and their dispersion as groups maintaining intense cultural contact across different regions. The sites in this analysis date back approximately ~1000 years before the present. Additionally, there is homogeneity in the Tupiguarani Tradition identified throughout Brazilian territory, particularly in the State of São Paulo (PEREZ, 2022, 2023).

The geographic relief of the State of São Paulo may have influenced the results of this analysis, with valleys and river basins surrounding and isolating certain spaces, along with the configuration of the Serra do Mar separating the coast from the inland. This could have contributed to the observed results, including the delayed European contact with indigenous populations inland. This delay led to subtle differentiation in material culture, potentially explaining the configurations that distinguish coastal and inland sites in this analysis.

Importantly, we dismiss the possibility of any bias in the data, as we present information on various aspects of pottery configuration (morphological, technological, and decorative aspects), accumulating a total of 567 analyzed characters.

Therefore, observing the distribution of the indices:

-The Consistency Index (CI) related to rim shape (0.44) presents the best consistency.

-The Consistency Index (CI) for painting (0.72) seems to be the best for understanding homologies associated with ethnogenesis and phylogenesis, indicating that over 70% of the analyzed data is associated with phylogenesis, while less than 30% is associated with ethnogenesis. This suggests that the development of painting is widely distributed in the territory of the State of Sao Paulo, originating from a common ancestor, and changes observed in the collections are minimally associated with contact with external groups.

-The Retention Index (RI) for all analyzed characters (0.62) and for temper (0.75) are the best, as they are the closest to 1, which is ideal for homologies.

However, although the indices suggest that the ideal representations would involve the distribution presented by all the characters together, followed by the temper index, the ideal tree configurations arise by observing the distribution of data in spatiality. Geographic proximity indicates greater similarity between the sites, as observed in the trees created from painting and surface treatment and finishes (trees 2, 3, 5, 6, 8, 10, 12), where the Mineração and Itaguá sites are highlighted among the inland sites. We also had the opportunity to chronologically position the sites Prema Tupi, Sao Geraldo/Sao Cardoso, Dourado 2, and De Rosa, suggesting proximity to the sites Pajeu, Lambari II, and Gramado.

Guided by the interpretations of Garcia-Rivero and O'Brien (2014), considering the results achieved from the Consistency and Retention Indices and the observations on cladistic trees, we can derive some explanations for the data:

1) These people freely inhabit the territory and use known technologies to produce their pottery.

2) There is some degree of cultural sharing or horizontal transfer of information among the population in the state of São Paulo, depending on the observed characters, presenting a phylogenetic signal in the samples analyzed. However, this must be observed carefully, as the numbers obtained through the observation of all characters and seasoning suggest a high phylogenetic signal, while information on graphics and external surface

finishing and treatment do not present satisfactory numbers. This observation in relation to numbers is justified, as in the cladogram, what is observed is information transmitted through teaching and learning, as is the case with the technique of inserting a certain seasoning into the clay, rather than information that can be quickly replicated, such as information on graphics, treatment, and surface finishes, which can generally be provided at an accelerated pace through other contacts between groups.

3) This population adheres to an ideological set used to produce pottery distributed throughout the territory of Sao Paulo, implying a cultural system in which design is involved in the technological and morphological production of vessels, based or was based on a fundamental central idea, surrounded by a series of changeable and variable elements. In line with the propositions elaborated by Tehrani and Collard (2002) and developed by Boyd, et al. (1997), these cultures present integrated hierarchical systems with central traditions and peripheral elements. Garcia-Rivero and O'Brien (2014) associated their results with a conservative aspect of culture called "core tradition," with a cultural tradition that includes aspects expressing historical relationships confined within specific geographic borders, as observed in this case. People learn from those culturally related and from those in contact, and both ideas and people move through the territory. Therefore, the structure presented in our results is expected.

In this way, the information was possibly much more widespread than a single cladogenic tree can explain from its branches. Thus, what is observed in the territory of the State of Sao Paulo is much more the phylogenetic expression of cultural change than an ethnogenetic vision of this change in material culture. This means that cultural change can be associated much more with a cultural differentiation that occurred over time from a common ancestor, rather than with a change caused by contact with another outside group. This explanation is corroborated by the homogeneity achieved and observed in the material culture of this population in the studied territory, with free and systematic use of a set of disseminated knowledge and ideological sharing.

All the considerations suggest that the experiments described here do not provide unique explanations about the dispersion of cultural traits throughout the State of Sao Paulo territory, but cladistics appears as an invitation to disciplined conjecture, or perhaps, an improved system of understanding for phylogenetic purposes, with a simple algorithm to guarantee a suggested answer.

The results achieved during the internship at the University of Auckland allowed us to build precious inferences about the occupation of the state of São Paulo, offering

arguments that will be disseminated through the articles that are currently being prepared. Again, we highlight the importance of collaboration possibilities between research groups to build perspectives on our data. All these collaborations will contribute to the main research studies of the responsible researcher. With the incorporation of the methods learned and new evaluations will be constructed based on the inclusion of other archaeological sites that have their collections analyzed and meet the needs of this approach. In this way, the objective established for the internship was successfully achieved, in which all planned activities were developed, especially the possibility of deepening specific readings, participation in discussion groups on relevant topics, courses and lectures, thus expanding knowledge about the most diverse perspectives and possibilities associated with the interdisciplinarity that Archaeology allows.

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Attached documents

- Activities developed at the University of Auckland;
- Articles in preparation;
- Book chapter accepted for publication
- Certificate of participation in an international event;